

Real industry technology learning systems for tertiary teaching

Amy Cosby¹, Richard Flavel*¹, Susan McDonnell², Sue Gregory¹ and Mark Trotter³

1 School of Education, University of New England, Armidale, Australia

2 GrainGrowers, Canberra, Australia

3 Institute for Future Farming Systems, Central Queensland University, Rockhampton, Australia

Abstract

A collaborative project between seven universities, the SmartFarm Learning Hub (the Hub) aims to increase the knowledge and skill base of students studying agriculture and agribusiness in the latest agri-tech tools and systems. One motivation for the Hub is the current skills shortage in the agricultural industry and the challenge for university education to keep pace with the rapidly developing agri-tech systems and tools. The Hub will host numerous learning modules which use real industry technology learning systems (RITLS) using real-farm data allowing students to learn how to apply industry developed or commercially available systems and tools to solve an agricultural problem or manage a complex system. By completing these learning modules, students' capability and readiness for employment within the agricultural industry will be increased. Reported are the evaluation of responses from students after completing the ProductionWise® learning module to the questions based on their perception of employability skills and practical content. Initial results demonstrate that the majority of students believe the content of the ProductionWise® practical is accurate and up-to-date with 87.5% of respondents either 'strongly agreeing' or 'agreeing' with this statement. The feedback received from students will be used to improve the instructions and content of the practical for future cohorts.

Background

The SmartFarm Learning Hub (the Hub) is a central website (www.smartfarmhub.com) hosting a series of learning resources (modules) that utilise 'Real Industry Technology Learning Systems' (RITLS) (Cosby et al., 2017) for tertiary teaching. The project is a collaboration between 7 universities, the majority are located in Australia; namely the University of New England, University of Tasmania, University of Central Queensland, University of Southern Queensland, University of Melbourne, University of Sydney and New Mexico State University. The main objective of the Hub is to increase students' 'work readiness' in regards to their skills and knowledge of the latest agri-tech tools and systems and their ability to use these in their future employment to improve the productivity, profitability and sustainability of agricultural enterprises (Trotter et al., 2016).

The Hub was developed in recognition of the concerns raised that the content of agricultural science and agribusiness degrees at universities is not resulting in graduates with the skills and knowledge required for the jobs currently available in the agricultural industry, or those that will be created in the future (Senate Standing Committees on Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2012). There is already a skills shortage in agriculture with Pratley and Botwright Acuna (2015) estimating that there are four jobs available for every tertiary agricultural graduate (Pratley and Botwright Acuna, 2015). Many agri-tech companies and industry organisations (e.g. GrainGrowers, Pasture.io, MaiaGrazing) have recognised these issues and have partnered with the Hub to develop RITLS learning modules. Reported in this paper is the preliminary student survey results evaluating one of the RITLS module, ProductionWise® is an online crop management tool developed for farmers by GrainGrowers, an independent grain grower representative organisation (GrainGrowers, 2017).

Methods

Students, undertaking degrees in Rural Science, Agriculture and Agribusiness, completed the three-hour ProductionWise® learning module as part of a third year agronomy unit, AGRO321 – Crop Production at the University of New England, Armidale, New South Wales, Australia. The learning module was developed by Dr. Richard Flavel, lecturer in Crop Science, and taught to a cohort of internal students in August 2016. Of the 50 internal students enrolled in the unit, 16 completed the survey, a response rate of 32%.

Developed by GrainGrowers, ProductionWise® is an online farm management tool, used particularly to manage crops, by farmers, agronomists and agricultural consultants (GrainGrowers, 2017). Students were required to use the mapping functions and CropTracker tool available as part of the ProductionWise® system to model the expected performance of current season winter wheat crops and explore the impacts of management decisions (e.g. fertiliser application irrigation) on yields predicted by the model. Figure 1 displays one of the CropTracker screen students analysed to answer questions on the practical sheet. Students were taught how this tool can be used to critically investigate the complex interactions between management decisions, crop physiology and environmental factors (e.g. available soil moisture, fertiliser applications and thermal drivers). Students were provided with scenarios from the Northern and Southern grain growing regions in Australia. They were tasked to respond and provide recommendations as though they were a consulting Agronomist or how to best manage the cropping system.

Figure 1. The ProductionWise® CropTracker predicting the yield of a wheat crop and the APSIM Soil Moisture model

Students were invited to complete an online survey, consisting of 34 questions, through SurveyMonkey® once they had completed the practical (Approval No. HE16-129). The questions assessed a range of aspects including the content, whether they perceived their employability skills had increased as a result of completing the practical, if they felt the threshold learning outcomes (derived from AgLTAS standards) (Botwright Acuña and Able, 2016) were achieved, their information and communication technologies (ICT) skills before and after, the system usability scale and general demographic questions. The majority of questions were asked using a Likert scale (Likert, 1932).

The data derived from the survey results will be used to improve the ProductionWise learning module for future cohorts as part of an action research cycle (Reason and Bradbury, 2001). The improved learning module will be taught to the 2017 cohort of AGRO321 students and it will again be evaluated to determine whether the amendments have increased student perception of the value of the practical.

Results and discussion

The results reported in this paper will focus on the questions related to the content of the learning module and the student's perception of whether their employability skills had increased after completing the ProductionWise® practical. Sixteen students completed the survey and table 1 displays the demographic information collected. Half of the respondents indicated that their place of residence is living on a rural property, however as the survey did not ask what type of agricultural enterprise (if any) was being conducted, we are unable to distinguish whether any of these students are from a cropping farm, and would potentially be familiar with ProductionWise®. The researchers will consider amending the survey to ask respondents what type of agricultural enterprise is present to determine whether there is a connection between prior knowledge and experience gained through an existing link to a cropping property, and results of the employability, learning outcome and practical content questions.

Table 1. Demographics of students who completed evaluation survey.

Gender	Response Count	Response Percent
Female	7	43.75%
Male	7	43.75%
No response	2	12.5%
Age	Response Count	Response Percent
18 to 21	5	31.25%
22 to 31	8	50%
32 to 41	1	6.25%
42 to 51	0	0%
52 to 61	0	0%
62 +	0	0%
No response	2	12.5%
Place of residence when not attending university	Response Count	Response Percent
Rural – living on land/property	8	50%
Rural Town – less than 5,000 people	1	6.25%
Town – 5,000-18,000 people	4	25%
Major City – 50,000-250,000 people	0	0%
Capital City – 250,000+ people	1	6.25%
No response	2	12.5%

Table 2 displays the responses from students to the three questions related to employability. Students were also asked whether they were likely to use the knowledge they developed from this practical in their future employment with 12.5% of students 'strongly agreeing' and 81.25% 'agreeing' they would (Table 2). When asked whether they believed by completing the ProductionWise® practical would increase their employability in the agricultural industry 12.5% of students 'strongly agreed' and 62.5% agreed (Table 2).

One student also commented:

Programs like this are increasingly used in agriculture it is important we know about them and how to use it.

However, when asked whether they believed their CV would increase in value when they added the skills they have learnt from this practical, the response was not as positive with 25% of respondents choosing to remain 'neutral' (Table 2). The responses received to this question for the ProductionWise® module are similar to those collected from the PA Source RITLS practical (Cosby et al., 2017). This suggests that more focus may be needed, for all RITLS modules hosted on the Hub, highlighting explicitly for students the key knowledge and skills they could develop as a result of completing the practical, which they can add to their CV. For example, one statement could be 'Familiarity with the ProductionWise® system and its capabilities to assist with making crop management decisions.' As a result of the initial evaluation of numerous RITLS modules in 2016, 2-3 brief statements will be added to all learning materials which students will have the option to add to their CV. It is hoped that by providing this information to students they will be more confident in developing their CV and recognise the value of completing RITLS modules during their university studies.

Table 2. Results of initial study looking at student responses to employability questions after completion of ProductionWise learning module

Employability questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Completing this practical will increase my employability in the agricultural industry	12.5%	62.5%	25.0%	0.0%	0.0%
I am likely to use the knowledge I have developed from this practical in my future employment	12.5%	81.25%	6.25%	0.0%	0.0%
My CV/resume will increase in value when I add the skills I have learnt from this practical	0.0%	68.75%	25.0%	0.0%	6.25%

Table 3 displays the results of the survey respondents to the questions which asked about the practical content. Overall, the responses to these questions were very positive with over 85% of students answering 'strongly agree' or 'agree' to all statements (Table 3). It is evident that students understood the content of the practical, felt it was accurate and up-to-date and importantly, appropriate to their knowledge and experience. The ProductionWise® module will be updated with winter crops planted in 2017 to ensure students are again working with real farm and current data.

This is important as the Hub aims to utilise as close to live data as possible to ensure the scenarios posed to students are very realistic. As students are using actual, up-to-date farm data in ProductionWise® they are also exposed to the complexity and messiness of real world environments which can be a challenge. There is some additional work involved for a lecturer to update the data in the module on an annual basis. However, a positive outcome of this is that the longer the module runs, the larger the database becomes allowing students to observe seasonal effects on a crop. It is possible that if the module ran for a decade educators could pick certain years to demonstrate the influence of season on a real farm.

Table 3. Results of initial study looking at student responses to questions about practical content after completion of ProductionWise learning module

Practical content	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The content of the practical is easily understood	6.25%	81.25%	6.25%	6.25%	0.0%
The content of the practical is accurate and up-to-date	25.0%	62.5%	6.25%	6.25%	0.0%
The level of content is appropriate to my knowledge and experience.	37.5%	62.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

The use of ProductionWise® as an educational activity as part of the Hub has been a learning experience for both GrainGrowers and academic staff at UNE. A key challenge with the broad scale utilisation of all RITLS learning modules on the Hub (including the ProductionWise module) is that considerable software customisation is often required to create a separate platform within an existing commercial system to accommodate linked learning accounts. Without this customisation, there is a heavy administrative burden placed on the technical team to create accounts for educational purposes. GrainGrowers has provided support for the Hub for the two years of the project and recognise that further investment is needed if the ProductionWise® software is to be used for educational purposes at a larger scale. At this time GrainGrowers does not have the resources to pursue this customisation but will consider it further down the track if the opportunity arises. This is a key issue that needs to be explored early on by universities and agri-tech companies wanting to work together to develop learning materials for educational purposes to ensure a mutually beneficial solution can be reached.

Conclusion

Preliminary results demonstrate that the ProductionWise® module is achieving its objective of increasing student's perception of their employability skills with 93.75% of respondents 'strongly agreeing' or 'agreeing' that they are likely to use the knowledge developed from completing the practical in their future employment. There is room for improvement to highlight key skills and knowledge which students could add to their CV. As the ProductionWise® practical is a component of a larger agronomy unit, the researchers recognise that students may not feel confident they have developed significant skills to add to their CV in one three-hour practical. The students who completed the survey also felt that the content of the practical is easily understood, accurate, up-to-date and pitched at the appropriate level. Further refinement of the ProductionWise® module, including adding statement which students can use on their CV to highlight the skills and knowledge developed, will occur for delivery to students in 2017.

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